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4 **Recovery of dissolved methane through a flat sheet module with PDMS, PP, and PVDF**
5 **membranes**

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11 **Abstract**

12 A degassing contactor using a flat sheet membrane module (FM) was operated in sweep gas
13 mode to study the performance of several commercial polymer membranes, both dense
14 (polydimethylsiloxane, PDMS) and microporous (polypropylene, PP, and
15 polyvinylidene fluoride, PVDF), for the recovery of dissolved methane from water. Non-steady
16 state experiments were conducted at different liquid (Q_L , 3.5–40.5 L h⁻¹) and gas flow rates
17 (Q_{N_2} , 0.05–15.00 L h⁻¹). In the case of PDMS, PP, and when PVDF was operated at moderate
18 high Q_L (≥ 21 L h⁻¹), similar methane removal efficiencies (RE) were obtained. In the case of
19 PVDF operated at relatively low Q_L (3.5 L h⁻¹), a lower RE was observed. A model for the mass
20 transfer of methane has been selected that is adequate in predicting the experimental results.
21 These results concluded that the mass transfer resistance was mainly located in the liquid phase.
22 Microscopy and especially contact angle measurements were used to monitor the structural and
23 surface stability on the membranes. The membranes were altered during the operation,

24 especially for $Q_L \geq 21 \text{ L h}^{-1}$, showing a decrease (PDMS and PP) or an increase (PVDF) in
25 hydrophobicity and even cleavages (PDMS). The combination of the FM and contact angle
26 technique has demonstrated to be very versatile and useful for monitoring the variation of the
27 membrane properties during operation.

28 **Keywords**

29 Methane recovery; Flat sheet membrane module; Polymeric membrane; Membrane stability;
30 Mass transfer

31 **1. Introduction**

32 The industrial implementation of a separation process based on membrane technology is
33 becoming increasingly important [1,2], resulting in a greater research attention in recent years
34 to the development of special membrane applications, such as pervaporation or gas-liquid
35 contactors [3]. These membrane-based processes combine the advantages of providing very
36 high contact area per unit volume and more flexibility in the operating conditions while
37 avoiding some of the drawbacks of conventional technologies (flooding, loading, weeping, or
38 foaming) [4]. In addition, the stated advantages are frequently complemented with high
39 separation selectivity typical for the absorption process [3]. In this context, the potential use of
40 membrane contactors in operations for the recovery of organic compounds from biological
41 process effluents has been recently highlighted [5,6]. There has been a special focus on methane
42 recovery from anaerobic effluents, with a considerable amount of comprehensive reviews
43 recently published [7–10]. Membrane contactors have proven to be a promising technology to
44 avoid the loss of dissolved methane (D-CH₄) in anaerobically-treated low-strength wastewater,
45 which could reach up to over one-third [11] of the produced methane, due to their attractive
46 characteristics, such as low energy consumption, good selectivity, or ease of engineering [12].
47 Nevertheless, several aspects related to resistance to fouling and wetting, durability, or

48 scalability must be solved before considering this technology to be at a sufficient level of
49 maturity to become a commercially available tool for this application.

50 There are two main configurations of membrane contactors: hollow fibre and flat sheet [13].
51 Although many studies have focused on the hollow fibre membrane contactors, surely due to
52 their compacity and cost-effectiveness, flat sheet membrane contactors can present several
53 advantages related to their simplicity and versatility (easy to clean and replace), which make
54 them attractive for their use in certain applications and in laboratory scale. Flat sheet membrane
55 contactors can be especially useful where the fouling or membrane stability is the focus of the
56 research or to facilitate the performance comparison of membrane materials with different
57 characteristics since the influence of the fibre diameter and fibre packing density on mass
58 transfer of hollow fibre configuration is avoided [13]. Flat sheet membrane studies have been
59 frequently reported in some membrane processes, such as desalination or water treatment [14],
60 but their use in methane recovery has not been reported. As previously stated, the influence of
61 membrane properties like structural and surface stability or fouling and wetting resistance might
62 be crucial for developing this particular application, and the use of flat sheet membranes could
63 facilitate this task.

64 The most common surface feature of polymeric membranes is the hydrophilicity-
65 hydrophobicity (wettability) since it has an important influence on their performance, like
66 permeate flux, membrane rejection, or membrane fouling. The surface wettability of
67 membranes can be determined by measuring the water contact angle, which depends on many
68 factors such as surface energy or roughness [15]. Hydrophobic membranes are preferred for gas
69 separation and purification applications since they favour the passage of gas and repel the entry
70 of water through them [16]. In this regard, the use of hydrophobic membrane surface

71 modifications to increase the wetting and fouling resistance [17,18] in the methane recovery
72 application has been reported.

73 In this context, one of the aims of the present work was to determine the applicability and
74 versatility (and also limitations) of a gas-liquid flat sheet membrane system based on our own
75 design for the recovery of D-CH₄ from water. For this purpose, the effect of the range of
76 operational conditions on the efficiency in methane recovery from water was determined, and
77 membranes with different materials and properties (porosity, thickness, hydrophobicity, etc.)
78 were tested. As a second aim, the durability and stability of membranes in this particular
79 application were compared and characterized.

80 The experimental validation of this system will allow its use in further studies for the
81 characterization of the fouling, cleaning strategies, stability, and durability of new or modified
82 membranes for dissolved methane recovery, and it could also be used for other gas-liquid
83 separations applications, such as pervaporation or membrane distillation.

84 **2. Materials and methods**

85 *2.1 Experimental setup and procedure*

86 A circular flat sheet membrane module (FM) made of stainless steel was designed for this work
87 (Fig. 1a and Fig. 1b). The main characteristics and dimensions of the FM are shown in Table 1.

88 A plastic spacer was coupled inside the FM to support the membrane to avoid deformation or
89 breakage. The module was designed to be operated at similar liquid velocities to that usually
90 applied in hollow fibre contactors [19], which favoured comparison purposes.

91 A lab scale system was assembled including the FM for degasification tests using a synthetic
92 D-CH₄ water stream (Fig. 1c). Initially, the different elements of the system were fully filled

93 with de-ionised water ($< 1 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$), the gas bubbles were purged, and a leak checking was
 94 carried out. A synthetic water stream was used in this work to simulate an anaerobic reactor
 95 effluent preventing the potential interferences of soluble or suspended compounds presented in
 96 this type of effluents.

97
 98 *Fig. 1. a) External and b) internal view of the flat sheet membrane module. c) Scheme of the*
 99 *experimental system for dissolved methane recovery from water with a flat sheet membrane*
 100 *module.*

101 *Table 1. Characteristics of the flat sheet membrane module*

Property	Value
Effective diameter, cm	4.7 *
Liquid channel width, mm	1.0
Gas channel width, mm	8.0
Liquid side hydraulic diameter, cm	0.2
Gas side hydraulic diameter, cm	1.3
Effective contact area, cm ²	17.3

* Delimited by the spacer

102
 103 In the first step of a degasification test, the water was saturated in a packed-bed absorption
 104 column with 99.5%_v CH₄ (Carbueros Metálicos, Spain) in a counter-current flux at atmospheric

105 pressure in the outlet. The column was built of methacrylate with an inner diameter of 6.5 cm,
106 an effective height of 50.0 cm, and filled with 1" pall rings (Refilltech, Germany). The CH₄
107 flow rate was fixed at 1000 mL min⁻¹ using a mass flow controller (Bronkhorst Hi-Tec, The
108 Netherlands) with a manometric pressure in the bottom of the column < 0.1 bar [19]. During
109 the saturation step, the on/off valve was kept opened and water was pumped from the bottom
110 of the column to the liquid feed tank in order to fill it with saturated water. The liquid feed tank
111 consisted of a 2 L glass bottle with a magnetic stirrer fixed at 500 rpm. The outlet water from
112 the tank was pumped to the FM, keeping its gas ports closed. Finally, the water from the FM
113 was discharged at the top of the column by means of the 3-way valve connecting the FM with
114 the column. Thus, the water was continuously recirculated in every part of the system with a
115 peristaltic pump (Watson-Marlow, USA.) operating in a closed loop (continuous line in Fig.
116 1c). The liquid flow rate ranged from 21 to 27 L h⁻¹ for the saturation step. The water saturation
117 was conducted at room temperature (23 ± 1 °C). A stable behaviour was observed after 1 h of
118 saturation, reaching a CH₄ concentration of 23.2 ± 3.4 mg L⁻¹, which is comparable to the CH₄
119 saturation in water, with a value of 23.8 mg L⁻¹ at 23 °C [20]. Similar CH₄ concentration values
120 were reported by other authors for degasification tests with synthetic liquid streams [21,22].

121 Once the saturation with CH₄ was reached, the saturation column was disconnected from the
122 rest of the system by closing the on/off valve and 3-way valve connecting the FM with the
123 liquid tank (loop in dotted line, Fig. 1c). Then, water saturated with CH₄ was stored in the liquid
124 feed tank. All experiments were carried out at the sweep gas mode using N₂ to generate a partial
125 pressure gradient for CH₄ and to recover the D-CH₄ in the gas form. For the degasification test,
126 the gas ports of the FM were opened and the N₂ mass flow controller was switched on. The
127 tested N₂ flow rates (Q_{N₂}) ranged from 0.05 to 15.00 L h⁻¹ supplied at atmospheric pressure (gas
128 velocity ranging from 0.0043 to 1.3 cm s⁻¹). No significant pressure drop (<0.01 bar) was
129 observed across the gas side of the FM. The liquid stream was pumped from the liquid feed

130 tank to the FM and then continuously recirculated to the tank operating in a closed loop (dotted
131 line in Fig. 1c). The liquid flow rates (Q_L) were fixed in values ranging from 3.5 to 40.5 L h⁻¹
132 (liquid velocity ranging from 2.8 to 32.5 cm s⁻¹). The tests were carried out at room temperature
133 (23 ± 1 °C). The duration of the unsteady experiments was usually 5 h, although some tests
134 were extended up to 22 h.

135 All the results shown in this work were obtained with liquid and sweep gas flowing in a cross
136 flow configuration, as shown in Fig. 1a. Remarkably, the experiments carried out with counter-
137 current flow showed no significant differences with respect to the cross flow configuration (see
138 Supplementary Material S1), showing that the flow configuration was not crucial in these
139 experiments.

140 Liquid and gas samples were periodically collected to analyse the evolution of the CH₄
141 concentration and to evaluate the performance of the system. Duplicates of liquid samples were
142 collected at the outlet of the liquid feed tank. Gas samples were taken from the outlet gas port
143 of the FM, which contained the recovered methane. A total of 3–6 samples were taken for liquid
144 and gas.

145 The liquid samples were analysed by a modification of the head-space method previously
146 described [19,23,24]. Shortly, 5 mL of the liquid samples were collected in sealed 16.0 mL
147 vials prefilled with air. These vials were placed in an orbital shaker at 200 rpm and 25 °C for
148 30 min. After this, 0.5 mL of the head-space gas was injected into a gas chromatograph (Agilent
149 GC 7820A, Spain) equipped with Agilent HP-PLOT/U and Agilent HP-MOLESIEVE columns
150 and a thermal conductivity detector. The CH₄ concentration in the liquid sample was determined
151 by applying Henry's Law:

152
$$C_{L,eq} = H^{cp} \cdot p^{p,eq} \cdot M_{CH_4} \quad (1)$$

153 where $C_{L,eq}$ ($\text{mg L}^{-1} \equiv \text{g m}^{-3}$) is the CH_4 concentration in the liquid in equilibrium with the head-
 154 space gas, $P^{p,eq}$ (Pa) is the partial pressure of CH_4 in the head-space in equilibrium with the
 155 liquid phase determined from the gas chromatography analysis, M_{CH_4} is the molar mass of CH_4
 156 (16 g mol^{-1}), and H^{cp} is the Henry's Law constant ($1.4 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ mol m}^{-3} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$ at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [20]). The CH_4
 157 concentration in the original liquid sample was determined as follows:

$$158 \quad C_L = \frac{C_{G,eq} \cdot V_G + C_{L,eq} \cdot V_L}{V_L} \quad (2)$$

159 where C_L and $C_{G,eq}$ (mg L^{-1}) are the CH_4 concentrations in the original sample and in the head-
 160 space of the analysis vials, respectively, and V_G and V_L (L) are the gas and liquid volumes
 161 inside the analysis vials, respectively.

162 The variation of the CH_4 removal efficiency (RE, %) was used to evaluate the performance of
 163 the CH_4 recovery process under unsteady state. RE is defined as:

$$164 \quad \text{RE} = \frac{C_{L0} - C_{Lt}}{C_{L0}} \cdot 100 \quad (3)$$

165 where C_{L0} and C_{Lt} (mg L^{-1}) are the CH_4 concentrations in the liquid at initial time ($t = 0$) and at
 166 time on stream (t) from the liquid feed tank, respectively. In Eq. (3), a negligible variation of
 167 the liquid volume flow rate was assumed.

168 A sampling point located in the outlet gas port of the FM was used to take 0.5 mL of recovered
 169 gas samples by means of a gas chromatography syringe, which were injected into the former
 170 gas chromatograph. The CH_4 content in the recovered gas (y_{CH_4} , %_v) was calculated by the
 171 following equation:

$$172 \quad y_{\text{CH}_4} = \frac{C_G}{\rho_{\text{CH}_4}} \cdot 100 \quad (4)$$

173 where C_G (mg L^{-1}) is the CH_4 concentration in the recovered gas and ρ_{CH_4} (mg L^{-1}) is the CH_4
 174 density.

175

176 *2.2 Flat sheet membranes*

177 Four commercial flat sheet membranes were tested: a dense polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS)
 178 supplied by Pervatech (The Netherlands), two types of microporous polypropylene (Accurel®
 179 PP-1E and PP-2EHF, 3M Liqui-Cel) supplied by Membrane GmbH (Germany), and a
 180 microporous polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) supplied by Dorsan Filtration (Spain). The PDMS
 181 membrane consisted of a support of porous polyester (PET) and polyimide (PI) and a superficial
 182 dense layer of PDMS. The PVDF membrane contained PET as the material substrate. Both
 183 polypropylene membranes (PP) had no support or substrate material. The properties of the
 184 membranes are listed in Table 2. As can be seen, all membranes presented a hydrophobic nature
 185 (water contact angle $> 90^\circ$). Most of the experiments to study the influence of the operational
 186 conditions were carried out with PDMS. PP and PVDF were used for comparison purposes.

187 *Table 2. Properties of the flat sheet membranes.*

	PDMS	PP-1E	PP-2EHF	PVDF
Structure	Dense	Microporous	Microporous	Microporous
Support	PI/PET	Non supported	Non supported	PET
Water contact angle, °	100.9 ± 0.8^f	145.3 ± 1.4^f	140.2 ± 4.1^f	103.4 ± 1.6^f
Bubble point, bar	-	2.1	0.7	1.8
Pore radius, μm	PDMS: - PI: 7.2 ± 2.1^a PET: 0.2	0.21 ^d	0.57 ^d	0.20
Thickness, μm	PDMS: 2.5 ± 0.1^a PI: 63.9 ± 5^a PET: 108.6 ± 5^a (Overall: 175 ± 5)	100 ± 15	170 ± 15	159 ± 2^a
Porosity	PDMS: - PI: 0.72 ± 0.01^a PET: 0.32 ± 0.05^a	0.44 ± 0.04^e	0.44 ± 0.04^e	0.74 ± 0.11^g
Tortuosity	PDMS: - PI: 2.25 ± 0.04^c PET: 9.02 ± 2.19^c	5.61 ± 1.12^c	5.61 ± 1.12^c	2.27 ± 1.00^c
CH₄ permeability,	PDMS: $7.13 \cdot 10^{-15}^b$	-	-	-

m² Pa⁻¹ s⁻¹

- 188 ^aAnalysed by FESEM images
189 ^bData from [25]
190 ^cCalculated by porosity-tortuosity relationship [26,27]
191 ^dCalculated from bubble point value [28]
192 ^eMean value from literature [19,21,29]
193 ^fMeasured with water contact angle technique
194 ^gMean value from literature [26,30,31]
195

196 Circular membrane samples were prepared with a diameter of 6.5 cm. They were clamped into
197 the FM by means of a rubber O-ring for leak-proof-seal so the membrane edge was fixed. The
198 membranes were reused, and their water contact angle was measured after 2–5 experiments in
199 order to check the membrane hydrophobicity.

200 *2.3 Mass transfer evaluation*

201 A mass transfer analysis of the transport of the CH₄ from the liquid phase to the gas phase was
202 performed. From the mass balance and Fick's First Law, the experimental overall mass transfer
203 coefficient ($K_{L,exp}$, m s⁻¹) based on the liquid phase was calculated with the following expression
204 [32,33]:

$$205 \quad K_{L,exp} = \frac{M_T}{A \cdot \rho \cdot t} \ln \left(\frac{C_{L0} - C_{L0}^*}{C_{Lt} - C_{Lt}^*} \right) \quad (5)$$

206 where M_T is the total liquid mass in the system (2.35 kg), A is the effective membrane area
207 (0.00173 m²), ρ (kg m⁻³) is the liquid density, t (s) is the time on stream, and C_{L0}^* and C_{Lt}^* (mg
208 L⁻¹) are the CH₄ concentrations in the liquid in equilibrium with the CH₄ content in the outlet
209 gas (C_G , mg L⁻¹) at initial time ($t = 0$) and time t , respectively, calculated from Henry's Law
210 ($C_L^* = C_G/H$, H being the dimensionless Henry's constant with a value of 29.55 at 25 °C [20]).
211 Some assumptions were taken for using Eq. (5): (i) a constant membrane permeability
212 coefficient and (ii) M_T was assumed constant due to the small quantity of CH₄ recovered (< 52
213 mg) [32]. The derivation of Eq. (5) is shown in Supplementary Material S2.

214 The overall mass transfer coefficient based on the liquid phase can be estimated using the
 215 resistance in series model for compounds transferring from the bulk liquid phase to the bulk
 216 gas phase ($K_{L,est}$, $m\ s^{-1}$) for a flat sheet membrane module [26]:

$$217 \quad R_{ov} = \frac{1}{K_{L,est}} = \frac{1}{k_L} + \frac{1}{H \cdot k_m} + \frac{1}{H \cdot k_G} = R_L + R_m + R_G \quad (6)$$

218 where k_L , k_m , and k_G ($m\ s^{-1}$) are the individual mass transfer coefficients of the liquid phase,
 219 membrane, and gas phase, respectively, R_{ov} ($s\ m^{-1}$) is the overall mass transfer resistance, and
 220 R_L , R_m , and R_G ($s\ m^{-1}$) are the individual mass transfer resistances of the liquid phase,
 221 membrane, and gas phase, respectively. The liquid mass transfer coefficient has been estimated
 222 from the following empirical equation obtained for a FM with similar characteristics [26]:

$$223 \quad Sh_L = \frac{k_L \cdot d_{hL}}{D_{M,L}} = 0.823 \cdot Re_L^{0.39} \cdot Sc_L^{1/3} \cdot \left(\frac{d_{hL}}{l}\right)^{0.075} \quad (7)$$

224 where Sh_L , Re_L , and Sc_L are the Sherwood, Reynolds, and Schmidt numbers of the liquid phase,
 225 respectively, d_{hL} (m) is the hydraulic diameter of the liquid side of the module, $D_{M,L}$ is the
 226 molecular diffusion coefficient of CH_4 in the liquid phase ($1.76 \cdot 10^{-9}\ m^2\ s^{-1}$ at 25 °C and 1 bar
 227 [34]), and l is the length of the module (m).

228 The gas mass transfer coefficient was also estimated with empirical equations obtained for
 229 similar flat sheet membrane modules [27,35]:

$$230 \quad k_G = \frac{Sh_G \cdot D_{M,G}}{d_{hG}} \quad (8)$$

$$231 \quad Sh_G = (Sh_0^4 + Sh_\infty^4)^{1/4} \quad (9)$$

$$232 \quad Sh_0 = 2.52 \quad (10)$$

$$233 \quad Sh_\infty = 0.808 \cdot Re_G^{0.405} \cdot Sc_G^{1/3} \quad (11)$$

234 where Sh_G , Re_G , and Sc_G are the Sherwood, Reynold, and Schmidt numbers of the gas phase,
 235 respectively, $D_{M,G}$ ($m^2 s^{-1}$) is the molecular diffusion coefficient of CH_4 in the gas phase, d_{hG} is
 236 the hydraulic diameter of the gas side (m), and Sh_0 and Sh_∞ are the limiting Sherwood numbers.
 237 In the gas side of the module, only N_2 as the sweep gas was applied; thus, molecular diffusion
 238 of CH_4 in the gas can be estimated as follows [36]:

$$239 \quad D_{M,G} = \frac{0.01013 \cdot T^{1.75} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{M_{N_2}} + \frac{1}{M_{CH_4}} \right)^{1/2}}{P \cdot \left[(\Sigma v)_{N_2}^{1/3} + (\Sigma v)_{CH_4}^{1/3} \right]^2} \quad (12)$$

240 where T (K) is the temperature of the test, M ($g mol^{-1}$) is the molar mass, P (Pa) is the pressure
 241 in the gas phase, and (Σv) is the especial atomic diffusion volume (17.90 for N_2 and 24.42 for
 242 CH_4 [37]).

243 The membrane mass transfer coefficient can be estimated for both porous and dense
 244 membranes. For porous structures, it was estimated as follows [27]:

$$245 \quad k_{m,porous} = \frac{D_{G,eff} \cdot \varepsilon}{\tau \cdot \delta} \quad (13)$$

246 where ε , τ , and δ (m) are the porosity, tortuosity, and thickness of the membrane or layer and
 247 $D_{G,eff}$ is the effective diffusion of the transferred species in the gas phase inside the pores, which
 248 was estimated as follows [38]:

$$249 \quad \frac{1}{D_{G,eff}} = \frac{1}{D_{M,G}} + \frac{1}{D_{G,Kn}} \quad (14)$$

250 where $D_{G,Kn}$ ($m^2 s^{-1}$) is the Knudsen diffusion coefficient of CH_4 through the pores, which can
 251 be calculated by Eq. (15) [39]:

$$252 \quad D_{G,Kn} = 97 \cdot r_p \cdot \left(\frac{T \cdot 1000}{M_{CH_4}} \right)^{1/2} \quad (15)$$

253 where r_p (m) is the pore radius. The pores were assumed to be completely filled with the sweep
254 gas, N_2 .

255 For the dense membrane, the following equation can be used to estimate the membrane mass
256 transfer coefficient [40]:

$$257 \quad k_{m,dense} = \frac{P_{m,CH_4} \cdot R \cdot T}{\delta \cdot v_m} \quad (16)$$

258 where P_{m,CH_4} is the permeability of CH_4 through the dense membrane ($7.1256 \cdot 10^{-15} \text{ m}^2 \text{ Pa}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
259 at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for PDMS [25]), R is the ideal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ m}^3 \text{ Pa mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), and v_m ($\text{m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
260 is the molar volume of CH_4 .

261 The membranes can be composed of more than one layer of different materials, as the PDMS
262 and PVFD tested in this study. The total membrane mass transfer coefficient can be estimated
263 by means of the resistance in series model with Eq. (17) [27].

$$264 \quad \frac{1}{k_m} = \sum_n \frac{1}{k_{m,layer\ n}} \quad (17)$$

265

266 *2.4 Membrane surface and structural stability*

267 In order to determine the operational lifetime of the membranes and potential surface and
268 structural modifications, the membranes were repeatedly used in sequential degassing
269 experiments for up to 200–300 h. The effect of the time on stream on the membrane
270 hydrophobicity was studied, as reported by Oldani et al. [41]. Thus, the surface modification of
271 the membrane hydrophobicity was monitored by periodical measurements of the water static
272 contact angle (CA). CA measurements were performed with a water drop of $5.5 \pm 0.1 \text{ } \mu\text{L}$ using
273 a syringe pump (KF Technology, USA) at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The image capture was taken at 15 s with a

274 digital microscope (Celestron Handheld Digital Microscope Pro, China) and white light (Philips
275 HUE Lamp, The Netherlands). Examples of CA images with pristine membranes are shown in
276 Supplementary Material S3. ImageJ software was used for image processing using the *Contact*
277 *Angle Plug-in* based on the ellipse approximation. A mean CA value was obtained from at least
278 6 measurements in different spots of the membranes. The CA values of the wet membranes
279 were measured after removing the excess water and moisture evaporation at room temperature
280 for approximately 1 h with forced aeration in the head.

281 The morphology of the membrane surface and cross-section was analysed using a Field
282 Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FESEM) equipped with an Energy Dispersive X-ray
283 Spectrometer (EDX) and applying an accelerating voltage of 20 kV (Hitachi S4800, Hitachi
284 Ltd., Japan). For image acquisition, the sample surfaces were previously coated with a fine
285 layer of Au/Pd by sputtering for 1 min.

286

287 **3. Results and discussion**

288 *3.1 Effect of operational parameters on the performance of dissolved CH₄ degassing* 289 *experiments*

290 The efficiency of the CH₄ recovery process can be mainly followed through the CH₄ removal
291 efficiency (RE). The effect of the operational parameters (Q_L and Q_{N_2}) on RE and CH₄ content
292 (y_{CH_4}) in the recovered gas is discussed in this section. Most of the experiments to study the
293 influence of liquid and N₂ flow rates on the RE and CH₄ content in the recovered gas were
294 performed with PDMS since this material is one of the most widely used at both lab and
295 industrial scale for degasification processes. Liquid flow rates (Q_L) of 3.5, 21.0, 27.0, and 40.5
296 L h⁻¹ and N₂ flow rates (Q_{N_2}) of 0.05, 0.50, 4.00, and 15.00 L h⁻¹ were used in these tests.

297 The profiles of RE with the degasification time are shown in Fig. 2a. Additionally, evolution of
 298 dissolved CH₄ concentration can be found in Supplementary Material S4. In these degassing
 299 tests, a constant N₂ flow rate of 0.5 L h⁻¹ was used at different liquid flow rates. The slope of
 300 the RE profiles and their values increased as Q_L increased. This result suggested that the liquid
 301 mass transfer resistance presented a critical role since increasing liquid flow velocity seemed
 302 to lead to an enhancement in performance. The RE reached values around 90% at 22 h on stream
 303 for Q_L ≥ 21.0 L h⁻¹. A lower RE of 59% was observed for the lowest Q_L of 3.5 L h⁻¹ at 22 h.
 304 The increase in RE was higher in the first 5 h on stream, and then, the RE increase was less
 305 pronounced. For instance, a RE value of 55% was observed at 5 h on stream for the highest Q_L
 306 (40.5 L h⁻¹), and RE only increased 40% for the next 17 h (RE of 95% at 22 h). That trend was
 307 also reported by Dutta et al. [42] in a liquid-liquid extraction of CH₄ with a FM. This could be
 308 explained by taking into account that the driving force was lower as the CH₄ concentration in
 309 the water stream decreased. From these results, the duration of the experiments (at which the
 310 performance was considerably different) was established in 3–5 h as standard for comparison
 311 purposes.

312

313 *Fig. 2. a) CH₄ removal efficiency and b) CH₄ content in the recovered gas versus time on*

314 *stream at different liquid flow rates and a constant N₂ flow rate of 0.5 L h⁻¹ with PDMS.*

315 The effect of the liquid flow rate on the removal efficiency can be seen in Fig. 3a at a constant
316 N_2 flow rate of 0.5 L h^{-1} at different times on stream. The RE continuously increased with Q_L
317 from values between 16% and 24% to 39% and 55% for liquid flow rates of 3.5 and 40.5 L h^{-1} ,
318 respectively. This trend was observed at any time on stream, and it can be explained by taking
319 into account the non-steady state condition of the experimental system. Thus, the water inside
320 the liquid feed tank was degassed at a higher rate as Q_L increased. In addition, it is well known
321 that mass transfer can be improved at higher liquid velocities, increasing the flux of the
322 transferred component [26,43,44]. On the contrary, other authors reported a lower RE with
323 increasing Q_L with a FM or hollow fibre membrane contactors in steady state systems
324 [23,35,45]. In those cases, the residence time governs the efficiency of the separation: as Q_L
325 increases, a lower residence time of the liquid in contact with the membrane is obtained.

326 In contrast to the effect of Q_L , the RE stayed almost constant for Q_{N_2} higher than 0.05 L h^{-1} , as
327 can be seen in Fig. 3b. A slight increase in the RE was observed for the lowest Q_{N_2} . For instance,
328 the RE increased from 40% to 45% when the Q_{N_2} increased from 0.05 to 0.5 L h^{-1} , respectively,
329 at 5 h on stream. For values of Q_{N_2} higher than 0.5 L h^{-1} , the RE stayed around 36%, 41%, and
330 46% at 3, 4, and 5 h on stream, respectively. In the case of PP-1E, similar results were obtained
331 (see Supplementary Material S5) and no significant effect of Q_{N_2} on the RE was observed with
332 this microporous membrane. All these results seem to indicate an almost negligible mass
333 transfer resistance of the gas phase at the tested operational conditions with no dependence on
334 the membrane structure (dense or porous). A similar trend was obtained by other authors
335 applying Q_{N_2} between 0 and 900 L h^{-1} in hollow fibre membrane contactors and the FM for
336 pervaporation processes [22,35,46].

337

338 *Fig. 3. Effect of a) liquid flow rate at a constant N₂ flow rate of 0.5 L h⁻¹ and b) N₂ flow rate*

339 *at a constant liquid flow rate of 27 L h⁻¹ on the CH₄ removal efficiency at different times on*

340 *stream with PDMS.*

341 The CH₄ content in the recovered gas for tests at a constant N₂ flow rate of 0.5 L h⁻¹ and at

342 different liquid flow rates is shown in Fig. 2b. Initially, the CH₄ content decreased quickly from

343 values higher than 3.0% to around 1.4% in the first 5 h on stream for Q_L ≥ 21.0 L h⁻¹. Then, the

344 decrease rate of the CH₄ content was lower. Thus, the effect of the time on stream on the CH₄

345 content followed the same trend observed for the RE. A CH₄ content near 0% was observed at

346 22 h on stream in accordance with the high RE values and lower driving force discussed

347 previously. This effect was not observed for a liquid flow rate of 3.5 L h⁻¹, where the CH₄

348 content decrease was very low during the whole experiment (a decrease from 0.8% to 0.5% at

349 1 and 22 h, respectively). A higher CH₄ content was observed as the liquid flow rate increased,

350 and the differences were more noticeable between 1 and 2 h of operation. For instance, a CH₄

351 content of 0.8, 1.9, 2.2, and 2.6% was observed at 1 h on stream for Q_L of 3.5, 21.0, 27.0, and

352 40.5 L h⁻¹, respectively. From 5 h of operation, the CH₄ content was very low (< 1.5%) and was

353 similar for experiments at Q_L between 21.0 and 40.5 L h⁻¹. The obtained CH₄ fluxes (J_{CH₄}, g s⁻¹

354 m⁻²) followed the same trend that CH₄ content, decreasing as the driving force decreased with

355 the time on stream from values of $118 - 36 \text{ g s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$ at 0 h to values lower than $11 \text{ g s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$ at
356 22 h with a constant Q_{N_2} of 0.5 L h^{-1} (results shown in Supplementary Material S4).

357 The CH_4 content in the recovered gas drastically decreased with increasing Q_{N_2} , which was also
358 observed in our previous work [19]. The CH_4 content was always under 0.4% and usually lower
359 than the detection limit ($< 0.05\%$) at N_2 flow rates $\geq 4.0 \text{ L h}^{-1}$ (see Supplementary Material S6).
360 In contrast, the CH_4 flux slightly increased from a Q_{N_2} of 0.5 to 4.0 L h^{-1} and stayed constant
361 $Q_{\text{N}_2} \geq 4.0 \text{ L h}^{-1}$, showing a maximum value of $128 \text{ g s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$ at 0 h and Q_{N_2} of 4.0 L h^{-1} (results
362 shown in Supplementary Material S4). That increase was more pronounced at the beginning of
363 the degasification test and negligible from a time on stream of 5 h. Thus, a low N_2 flow rate
364 may be applied in order to maximize the CH_4 content in the recovered gas, remaining a high
365 performance of the membrane module.

366

367 *3.2 Effect of membrane materials on the performance of dissolved CH_4 degassing experiments*

368 For comparison purposes, experiments with microporous PVDF and two types of PP
369 membranes were also performed. The results obtained for PDMS and PP in the degassing tests
370 carried out with a liquid and N_2 flow rate of 21.0 and 0.5 L h^{-1} , respectively, are compared in
371 Fig. 4a. Similar RE values for the three membranes operating in the FM with values between
372 42% and 46% at 5 h on stream were obtained. The CH_4 content in the recovered gas was also
373 quite similar, decreasing from initial values between 2% and 3% to around 1% at 5 h on stream
374 for PP and PDMS (see Supplementary Material S7).

375

376 *Fig. 4. CH₄ removal efficiency versus time on stream with different membrane materials at a*
 377 *constant liquid flow rate of 21 L h⁻¹ and a N₂ flow rate of a) 0.5 L h⁻¹ for PDMS, PP-1E, and*
 378 *PP-2EHF and b) 4.0 L h⁻¹ for PDMS, unaltered PVDF (uPVDF), and altered PVDF*
 379 *(aPVDF). aPVDF was operated for at least 5 h at Q_L of 21.0 L h⁻¹ before the experiment.*

380 Higher REs and CH₄ content could be expected for microporous membranes due to a lower
 381 mass transfer resistance, as observed in hollow fibre contactors [17,29,45]. In contrast, the
 382 studies of Dingemans et al. [27] concluded that lower membrane mass transfer resistances can
 383 be obtained with dense membranes with a high gas permeability in experiments conducted in
 384 FMs. These authors used a flat sheet PDMS with an active layer between 2.0–2.5 μm similar to
 385 what was used in this work, whereas most mass transfer studies that are carried out with a
 386 PDMS hollow fibre contactor use a typical thickness between 110–2000 μm [23,43,44]. In this
 387 regard, Sethunga et al. [17] also reported greater performances with porous hollow fibre
 388 membranes possessing a dense thin film of PDMS than those with a thicker PDMS layer.
 389 Therefore, conclusions on the importance of membrane resistance could be affected by this fact,
 390 and a compromise between structural stability and performance must define the thickness of
 391 the membrane and their different layers.

392 Results obtained with PVDF can be seen in Fig. 4b, along with PDMS, at a constant N₂ flow
393 rate of 4.0 L h⁻¹ and different liquid flow rates. The RE of the PVDF increased with the total
394 time of use of the membrane when a Q_L ≥ 21.0 L h⁻¹ was applied. Thus, a different RE was
395 observed for what we called unaltered PVDF (uPVDF, operated always under a Q_L < 21 L h⁻¹
396 or with a time of use ≤ 5 h at Q_L ≥ 21.0 L h⁻¹) and for altered PVDF (aPVDF, operated at Q_L ≥
397 21.0 L h⁻¹ for at least 5 h). Thus, the RE obtained with the aPVDF was higher than the uPVDF
398 and similar to those obtained with PDMS, as can be seen in Fig. 4b. For example, REs of 39%
399 and 48% were obtained with uPVDF and aPVDF, respectively, at Q_L of 21.0 L h⁻¹. The lowest
400 REs were obtained for microporous uPVDF at all tested conditions, and results at a lower Q_L
401 of 3.5 L h⁻¹ are shown in Supplementary Material S8. The results suggested that the membrane
402 mass transfer resistance of uPVDF cannot be neglected. As will be discussed in a later section,
403 surface changes on uPVDF were observed after 5 h of time of use at Q_L ≥ 21.0 L h⁻¹, increasing
404 their hydrophobicity and performance. No similar observations have been reported in the
405 literature. The performance of the rest of the membranes (PDMS, PP-1E, and PP-2EHF) stayed
406 constant for a total time of use up to 100–300 h if no breakages on the surface appear. Thus, a
407 greater stability can be inferred.

408

409 *3.3 Membrane surface and structural stability*

410 The membrane inside the FM could be subjected to changes due to the stress caused by the
411 liquid flow [47]. Hydrophobicity evaluation, measured as water contact angle (CA), has been
412 frequently used to monitor the surface membrane stability and durability [41].

413 The CA variation versus time of use at Q_L of 21 L h⁻¹ (liquid velocity of 16.8 cm s⁻¹) for different
414 membranes is shown in Fig. 5a. The CA of PDMS was monitored until water breakthrough was

415 detected at 95 h of total time of use. A slight decrease in CA from 101° to 94° at 0 and 95 h,
 416 respectively, was observed for PDMS. The inspection of the membrane surface with FESEM
 417 revealed the presence of cleavages on the top active layer, which was in contact with the liquid
 418 flow (see Supplementary Material S9). In addition, delamination of the membrane dense layer
 419 was observed, losing the adhesion force between the PDMS layer and support, showing that at
 420 least for this type of membrane and at the tested operational conditions ($Q_L = 21.0 \text{ L h}^{-1}$), this
 421 material suffered critical damage. From cross-section images, the delamination effect was
 422 appreciated as the top layer was not adhered on the support layer. More severe delamination
 423 and cracks were observed by other authors for flat sheet composite membranes with a top dense
 424 layer of polyamide in forward osmosis processes at liquid velocities around 26.0 cm s^{-1} [47].
 425 Nevertheless, the RE for CH_4 recovery was not significantly affected for this loss of stability,
 426 up to cracks appeared on membrane.

427

428 *Fig. 5. Membrane water contact angle versus time of use for different membrane materials at*
 429 *a liquid flow rate of a) 21 L h⁻¹ and b) 3.5 L h⁻¹. uPVDF: unaltered PVDF; aPVDF: altered*
 430 *PVDF.*

431 In contrast, the CA stayed almost constant around 102° for PDMS at a Q_L of 3.5 L h^{-1} (liquid
 432 velocity of 2.8 cm s^{-1}) (Fig. 5b), and no signal degradation was detected. In conclusion,

433 mechanical degradation is suggested as the main cause for the stability loss of the PDMS at
434 liquid flow rates higher than 3.5 L h^{-1} .

435 The stability of the CA of the PP membranes was strongly altered in our experiments since a
436 large decrease in their CA in the first 5 h of time of use was observed at an intermediate Q_L of
437 21 L h^{-1} . The CA of PP-1E and PP-2EHF decreased from 145° to 105° and 140° to 122° ,
438 respectively (Fig. 5a). The loss of hydrophobicity could be also related to the high visual
439 deformation observed on these membranes. Since no support was contained in the PP
440 membranes, the mechanical resistance seemed to be lower than those with a support layer, such
441 as PDMS or PVDF. Thus, it seems that the design of the fluid channels and spacer of the FM
442 could play a critical role in this type of membrane in order to avoid high shear stress resulting
443 in membrane deformation [48].

444 Regarding the stability of the PVDF (Fig. 5), an increase in the hydrophobicity of the aPVDF
445 was obtained with the time of use at the highest Q_L (21.0 L h^{-1}). A gradual CA increase from
446 103° to 118° was observed during the first 70 h of use, and then, the CA stabilized to values
447 around 115° from 90 h (Fig. 5a). FESEM images showed a less porous surface for that aPVDF
448 with a higher CA (Fig. 6) with respect to the uPVDF, therefore substantial structural changes
449 on the membrane surface occurred at Q_L of 21.0 L h^{-1} . That phenomenon may be attributed to
450 a plastic deformation due to the stress induced by the liquid flow on the membrane. In contrast,
451 the CA of uPVDF stayed almost constant with values around 103° at a lower Q_L of 3.5 L h^{-1}
452 even though a higher surface heterogeneity was observed with values between 100° and 112° at
453 176 h (Fig. 5b).

454

455 *Fig. 6. Surface FESEM images of the a) pristine-unaltered PVDF and b) altered PVDF.*
456 *Altered PVDF was operating for 150 h at a liquid flow rate (Q_L) of 21.0 L h^{-1} before the*
457 *image acquisition.*

458 As previously discussed, higher REs were obtained in degasification tests with aPVDF after its
459 hydrophobicity was increased with respect to uPVDF (Fig. 4b). The hydrophobicity increase
460 and surface porosity decrease favoured the CH_4 flux across the membrane, decreasing the mass
461 transfer resistance. From these results, it can be concluded that the stability changes on the
462 aPVDF structure improved the performance of the CH_4 recovery. On the contrary, Kim et al.
463 [48] reported that deformation or structural changes on a flat sheet membrane of cellulose
464 reduced the performance of an osmosis process.

465 Studies about the performance stability of the membranes during operation for flat sheet
466 membranes are relatively scarce in the literature. In this regard, long-term tests have been
467 reported to evaluate the wetting resistance of modified membranes using the CH_4 flux as the
468 control parameter [30,49]. Other authors also reported membrane breakages in hollow fibre
469 membrane contactors [50,51]. Taking into account this relatively scarce information, it seems
470 that studies on the membrane stability changes are needed to enhance and deepen the knowledge
471 of this effect on the membrane performance in order to establish the limiting operational
472 condition and the useful lifetime of the membranes. For this purpose, the results suggest that

473 CA measurements could be a useful methodological approach to determine the stability of
474 membranes after their use.

475

476 *3.4 Mass transfer analysis*

477 A study of the mass transfer process for CH₄ separation was carried out in order to evaluate the
478 influence of the different operational conditions and membranes and validate the proposed
479 empirical model. The experimental and estimated values of the overall and individual mass
480 transfer coefficients are presented and evaluated in this section.

481 From the estimated values with Eq. (6) – Eq. (17), the lowest individual mass transfer
482 coefficients were always obtained for the liquid phase ($k_{L,est}$), indicating that the main mass
483 transfer resistance was located in the liquid phase. $k_{L,est}$ values ranging from $2.25 \cdot 10^{-5}$ to
484 $5.87 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ (see Supplementary Material S10) were obtained. The estimated mass transfer
485 resistance (R_G) of the gas phase represented less than 0.05% of the overall mass transfer
486 resistance (R_{ov}), with $k_{G,est}$ values between $369 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and $403 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$. Higher values were
487 reported by Dingemans et al. [27] for the separation of volatile organic compounds (VOCs)
488 from gas streams in a FM with an experimental coefficient ranging from $1500 \cdot 10^{-5}$ to $1900 \cdot 10^{-5}$
489 m s^{-1} in the permeate side by applying higher Q_{N_2} between 12–60 L h⁻¹. Thus, the mass transfer
490 resistance of the gas phase may be neglected for a FM under the tested operational condition.
491 These results are in agreement with previous studies carried out with PDMS and PP hollow
492 fibre contactors where the gas phase resistance was also considered negligible [45,52].

493 Regarding the estimated membrane mass transfer coefficient, the lowest $k_{m,est}$ was observed for
494 the dense PDMS, with a value around $30 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$; so, the membrane mass transfer resistance
495 (R_m) represented 0.5% of the R_{ov} . $k_{m,est}$ values of around $1549 \cdot 10^{-5}$, $911 \cdot 10^{-5}$, and $4247 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m}$

496 s^{-1} were obtained for PP-1E, PP-2EHF, and PVDF, respectively, with R_m representing less than
497 0.02% of the R_{ov} . As expected, the R_m was higher for PDMS due to its dense structure even
498 though k_m had a negligible effect on the final value of $K_{L,est}$ and, therefore, on R_{ov} . In the case
499 of the separation of VOCs from gas streams in a FM, experimental membrane mass transfer
500 coefficient ($k_{m,exp}$) values of around $300 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ were reported for composite porous
501 PP/PVDF membranes [27] and around $450 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ for composite porous membranes with a
502 $2 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ dense layer of PDMS. It is noteworthy to highlight that the increase in membrane
503 thickness leads to a decrease in the membrane mass transfer coefficient. Thus, a lower $k_{m,exp}$
504 value of around $1 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ has been reported for PDMS hollow fibre contactors with a
505 thickness of $110 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ for CH_4 degassing, representing up to 20% of the overall mass transfer
506 coefficient [44]. Membrane mass transfer coefficients with values ranging from 10^{-1} to 10^{-4} m
507 s^{-1} have been, indeed, reported for membranes with similar characteristics [40]. According to
508 the obtained results, it seems that the R_m could be neglected for microporous and dense
509 membranes with a low thickness ($\leq 2.5 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$) at least for liquid velocities no much higher than
510 that used in this work.

511 From the negligible effect of the estimated membrane and gas phase mass transfer resistance,
512 it seems reasonable that similar values of CH_4 removal efficiency would be obtained at similar
513 liquid hydraulic conditions for different membranes. As seen in Fig. 4, the obtained REs were
514 similar for PDMS, the two types of PP, and aPVDF with values around 45%.

515 The experimental overall mass transfer coefficient ($K_{L,exp}$) was calculated for all tested
516 operational conditions with values ranging from $1.66 \cdot 10^{-5}$ to $6.28 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$. No previous
517 references were found in the literature for D- CH_4 recovery by means of FMs, whilst hollow
518 fibre membrane contactors have been widely studied for CH_4 recovery. Using hollow fibre
519 contactors, $K_{L,exp}$ values between $0.16 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and $12.6 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ have been reported for most

520 typical membranes applied for CH₄ degassing as PDMS, PP, and PVDF at similar liquid
521 velocities used in this work [10]. Slightly lower $K_{L,exp}$ values were observed for dense
522 membranes than for porous membranes at similar liquid velocities in hollow fibre contactors,
523 and consequently, lower REs were reported [53].

524 Due to the scarcity of studies about D-CH₄ recovery with flat sheet membranes, the mass
525 transfer analysis of CH₄ degassing could only be compared with that of O₂ degassing [10]. A
526 $K_{L,exp}$ value of $6.3 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ was reported with a PP in FMs for dissolved O₂ removal from
527 water [54]. Also, $K_{L,exp}$ values between $0.95 \cdot 10^{-5}$ to $1.55 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ have been reported for O₂
528 absorption with PVDF [26], similar to those obtained in this work for D-CH₄ recovery.
529 Regarding O₂ transport through hollow fibre contactors, $K_{L,exp}$ values between $0.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and
530 $19 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ have been reported for a PP hollow fibre contactor at liquid velocities lower than
531 0.02 cm s^{-1} (liquid flow rates between 0.1 and 0.6 L h⁻¹) [54]. Other authors reported higher
532 $K_{L,exp}$ for O₂ removal with values ranging from $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ to $1 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ with a PP hollow fibre
533 contactor at higher liquid velocities between 38 and 80 cm s⁻¹ [55]. They associated the large
534 $K_{L,exp}$ values to the low packing density of their hollow fibre contactors, getting better contact
535 between the fibres and water and avoiding the channelling effect. In addition, $K_{L,exp}$ values
536 between $3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and $6 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ have been reported for CO₂ absorption from a gas stream with
537 a porous PP hollow fibre contactor at liquid velocities ranging from 10 to 50 cm s⁻¹ [56].

538 The experimental and estimated overall mass transfer coefficient clearly increased with liquid
539 flow rate, as shown in Fig. 7. These results showed a strong influence of the R_L on R_{ov} , as
540 previously discussed. Similar $K_{L,exp}$ and $K_{L,est}$ values were obtained when PDMS was used (Fig.
541 7a and Fig. 7b), so the model based on the empirical equations used for the mass transfer
542 analysis seems suitable for the prediction of the mass transfer resistance. The obtained values
543 for $K_{L,exp}$ were significantly lower than $K_{L,est}$ for uPVDF at all tested liquid flow rates (Fig. 7c)

544 even though the estimated values showed a similar behaviour to PDMS since the main mass
 545 transfer resistance was in the liquid phase. These results seem to indicate that R_m was
 546 underestimated for uPVDF. In contrast, similar $K_{L,exp}$ and $K_{L,est}$ values were obtained for a
 547 aPVDF with a time of use ≥ 5 h at Q_L of 21.0 L h^{-1} (Fig. 7c). In this case, the obtained results
 548 agree with the negligible R_m estimated and with the REs obtained for the aPVDF, similar to
 549 those obtained for PDMS and PP (Fig. 4). Thus, an additional mass transfer resistance on the
 550 uPVDF seemed to be initially present, which was permanently removed at a liquid flow rate of
 551 21.0 L h^{-1} .

552

553 *Fig. 7. Overall mass transfer coefficient versus liquid flow rate: a) for PDMS at a N₂ flow*
 554 *rate of 0.5 L h^{-1} and b) 4.0 L h^{-1} and c) for unaltered PVDF (uPVDF) and altered PVDF*
 555 *(aPVDF) at a N₂ flow rate of 4.0 L h^{-1} . aPVDF was operated for at least 5 h at 21.0 L h^{-1}*
 556 *before the experiments.*

557 The wetting phenomenon (pores partially or totally fill with the liquid phase) has been reported
 558 as one of the major drawbacks for microporous membranes since the liquid inside the
 559 membrane pores creates an additional resistance [57]. The CH_4 mass transfer rate decreases
 560 since the stagnant water in the pores replaces the gas, so R_m may represent up to 50% of the R_{ov}
 561 and can be significant even at the low pore fraction occupied by the liquid [53,58]. In the case
 562 of the PVDF studied in this work, the reduction of the surface porosity of uPVDF from values

563 ~75% to a dense-like surface for aPVDF (Fig. 6) and its hydrophobicity increase (Fig. 5) were
 564 in agreement with surfaces more resistant to wetting, removing the additional membrane mass
 565 transfer resistance.

566

567 *Fig. 8. Overall mass transfer coefficient versus N_2 flow rate for a) PDMS at a constant liquid*
 568 *flow rate of 27 L h^{-1} and b) PP-1E at a constant liquid flow rate of 21 L h^{-1} .*

569 As previously discussed, $K_{L,\text{est}}$ was not influenced by the N_2 flow rate. For PDMS, experimental
 570 $K_{L,\text{exp}}$ stayed almost constant at around $4.8 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ (Fig. 8a) for all tested Q_{N_2} . For PP-1E,
 571 $K_{L,\text{exp}}$ was also underestimated, showing values slightly lower than those estimated for all tested
 572 operational conditions (Fig. 8b). $K_{L,\text{exp}}$ values around $4.1 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and $K_{L,\text{est}}$ of $4.5 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$
 573 were obtained for PP-1E. In contrast, for PP-2EHF, similar values of $K_{L,\text{exp}}$ and $K_{L,\text{est}}$ were
 574 observed ($4.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and $4.5 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$, respectively) at the tested operational condition with
 575 liquid and N_2 flow rates of 21.0 and 0.5 L h^{-1} , respectively.

576

577 **4. Future research and practical implications**

578 The validation of a system based on a gas-liquid membrane contactor using a flat sheet
579 membrane module has been shown in this work. Besides the degassing of methane from
580 aqueous streams it could be also used in other applications such as stripping and gas absorption
581 from air or flue gas (liquid-gas system), gas removal from aqueous solutions using trans-
582 membrane chemical absorption (liquid-gas-liquid system) and removal of solubilized ions from
583 water (liquid-liquid system) [59,60].

584 Due to its configuration and structure (small size of the flat module), this system can facilitate
585 and enable future research focused both on the influence of different membrane properties, in
586 particular those related to hydrophobicity, fouling resistance or cleaning strategies, and on the
587 membrane characterization during its use, including fouling deposits or surface stability. In
588 contrast to hollow fibre contactors, in flat sheet modules the membrane can easily be extracted,
589 analysed and cleaned during operation and/or replaced, allowing considerable time and cost
590 savings.

591 Hollow fibre contactors are frequently recommended for industrial applications, because
592 usually they provide higher volumetric mass transfer coefficients and involve fewer capital
593 costs than flat membrane contactors. Nevertheless, hollow fibre module cannot be easily
594 repaired, which could lead to a non-negligible operational and maintenance cost and restrict its
595 feasibility in certain applications where membrane can be damaged or loss its properties. In
596 contrast, the replacement or cleaning of membrane can be easily carried out in flat sheet
597 modules. In order to compare the viability of both contactor configurations, suitable economic
598 analyses might be tackled considering all these aspects.

599 **5. Conclusions**

600 The applicability and versatility of a gas-liquid flat sheet membrane module based on our design
601 have been checked for the process of recovery of dissolved methane from water. PDMS, two
602 types of PP, and PVDF membranes were tested and compared at different liquid flow rates
603 (ranging from 3.5 to 40.5 L h⁻¹) and N₂ flow rates (ranging from 0.05 to 15.00 L h⁻¹). The
604 methane removal efficiency increased with the liquid flow rate for all tested operational
605 conditions and membranes. In contrast, the removal efficiency was not influenced by N₂ flow
606 rates higher than 0.05 L h⁻¹. A maximum removal efficiency of 95% was observed at 22 h of
607 time on stream with the highest liquid flow rate of 40.5 L h⁻¹ with PDMS.

608 Similar removal efficiencies were observed with dense PDMS and microporous PP membranes
609 and when a microporous PVDF membrane was tested at a moderate-high liquid flow rate (21
610 L h⁻¹). On the contrary, the microporous PVDF membrane operated at the lowest liquid flow
611 rate (3.5 L h⁻¹) showed lower removal efficiencies.

612 As expected, the mass transfer model for methane transport based on empirical equations agreed
613 with most of the experimental results. This mass transfer analysis showed that the main transfer
614 resistance was located in the liquid phase and that membrane and gas phase mass transfer were
615 negligible.

616 The evaluation of the membrane stability showed that PDMS suffered a slight decrease in
617 hydrophobicity at moderate liquid flow rates (21 L h⁻¹) even though the efficiency of the
618 methane recovery was unaltered, and finally, cleavages appeared in the membrane at almost
619 100 h of time on stream. The hydrophobicity of PP membranes also strongly decreased with
620 the time on stream, suggesting structural changes due to the membrane deformation. In the case
621 of PVDF, a different behaviour was observed since an increase in the hydrophobicity of the

622 membrane was observed when it was operated at a liquid flow rate of 21 L h⁻¹ for at least 5 h,
623 which agreed with the improvement in performance. This behaviour could be related to the
624 changes in superficial porosity when a moderate liquid flow rate was applied. These results also
625 suggest that water contact angle measurements, as a hydrophobicity indicator, could be a useful
626 parameter to infer the stability of membranes during their operations, especially in processes
627 where the membrane resistance is negligible.

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646 Methodology, Validation, Project administration, Writing - review & editing, Supervision.

647

648 **Conflicts of interest**

649 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
650 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

651

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Supplementary Material for

Recovery of dissolved methane through a flat sheet module with PDMS, PP and PVDF membranes

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S1. Effect of liquid-gas flow configuration on performance

Fig. S 1. Dissolved methane removal efficiency (RE, %) versus time on stream in degassing tests for different liquid-gas flow configurations with PDMS at liquid and sweep gas flow rate of 21.0 L h^{-1} and 4.0 L h^{-1} , respectively.

S2. Derivation of the equation for the experimental overall mass transfer coefficient

Experimental overall mass transfer coefficient ($K_{L,exp}$, $m\ s^{-1}$) can be calculated from the Fick's First Law [1,2]:

$$J_{CH_4} = K_{L,exp} \cdot \Delta C_L \quad (\text{Eq. S1})$$

where J_{CH_4} ($kg\ m^{-2}\ s^{-1}$) is the CH_4 flux through the membrane and ΔC_L represents the driving force for CH_4 transport calculated based on the liquid phase.

In our system, a mass balance for methane in the liquid phase can be defined as follow:

$$J_{CH_4} = -\frac{1}{A} \frac{dM_{CH_4}}{dt} \quad (\text{Eq. S2})$$

$$-\frac{dM_{CH_4}}{dt} = \frac{M_T}{\rho_b} \frac{d\Delta C_L}{dt} + \frac{\Delta C_L}{\rho_b} \frac{dM_T}{dt} \quad (\text{Eq. S3})$$

where M_{CH_4} (kg) is the CH_4 mass, M_T (kg) is the total mass of the treated water, A (m^2) is the effective membrane area, t (s) is the time on stream of the degasification test and ρ_b ($kg\ m^{-3}$) is the density of the liquid stream. M_T was assumed constant due to the small quantity of dissolved CH_4 recovered ($< 52\ mg$) respect to the total mass of water in the system (2.35 kg). In addition, ρ_b may be assumed equal to water density (ρ_w , $1000\ kg\ m^{-3}$) due to the low dissolved CH_4 concentration. Thus, Eq. S1, Eq. S2 and Eq. S3 can be combined resulting in the following differential equation:

$$-\frac{M_T}{\rho_w} \frac{d\Delta C_L}{dt} = A \cdot K_{L,exp} \cdot \Delta C_L \quad (\text{Eq. S4})$$

The driving force based on liquid phase can be defined as $\Delta C_L = C_L - C_L^*$, where C_L and C_L^* ($mg\ L^{-1} \equiv g\ m^{-3}$) are the CH_4 concentration in the liquid feed and in the liquid in equilibrium with the CH_4 content in the outlet gas, respectively. Assuming a constant membrane permeability for methane ($K_{L,exp} \approx \text{constant}$), the integration of the differential equation Eq. S4 results as follow:

$$- \int_{\Delta C_0}^{\Delta C_t} \frac{d\Delta C_L}{\Delta C_L} = \frac{K_{L,exp} \cdot A \cdot \rho_w}{M_T} \int_0^t dt \quad (\text{Eq. S5})$$

$$K_{L,exp} = \frac{M_T}{A \cdot \rho_w \cdot t} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{C_{L0} - C_{L0}^*}{C_{Lt} - C_{Lt}^*} \right) \quad (\text{Eq. S6})$$

Although, in most of the experiments, where $C_L \gg C_L^*$, this equation could be simplified to:

$$K_{L,exp} = \frac{M_T}{A \cdot \rho_w \cdot t} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{C_{L0}}{C_{Lt}} \right) \quad (\text{Eq. S7})$$

S3. Contact angle images

Static water contact angle measurements were carried out for pristine PDMS, PP-1E, PP-2EHF and PVDF in order to determine their hydrophobicity and monitor their superficial and structural stability.

Fig. S 2. Water droplets for static contact angle measurements for pristine a) PDMS, b) PVDF, c) PP-1E and d) PP-2EHF.

S4. Effect of the time on stream and nitrogen flow rate on the methane flux and dissolved methane concentration

Fig. S 3. Dissolved methane concentration (C_L) in the liquid stream versus time on stream at different liquid flow rates (Q_L) at a constant nitrogen flow rate (Q_{N2}) of 0.5 L h^{-1} in degassing tests carried out with PDMS.

Fig. S 4. Methane flux versus a) time on stream at different liquid flow rates (Q_L) and at constant nitrogen flow rate (Q_{N2}) of 0.5 L h^{-1} and b) Q_{N2} at different time on stream and at constant Q_L of 27 L h^{-1} in degassing tests carried out with PDMS.

S5. Effect of sweep gas flow rate on removal efficiency for microporous PP-1E

Fig. S 5. Dissolved methane removal efficiency (RE, %) versus sweep gas flow rate (Q_{N_2} , L h⁻¹) at different time on stream and at a constant liquid flow rate (Q_L) of 21 L h⁻¹ in degassing tests carried out with PP-1E.

S6. Effect of sweep gas flow rate on methane content for PDMS

Fig. S 6. Methane content (y_{CH_4} , %) versus time on stream of degassing tests at different sweep gas flow rates (Q_{N_2} , L h^{-1}) with PDMS at a constant liquid flow rate (Q_L) of 3.5 L h^{-1} .

S7. Effect of membrane material on methane content

Fig. S 7. Methane content (y_{CH_4} , %) in the recovered gas versus time on stream of degassing tests with different membranes at a liquid (Q_L , $L h^{-1}$) and sweep gas flow rate (Q_{N_2} , $L h^{-1}$) of 21.0 and 3.5 $L h^{-1}$, respectively.

S8. Effect of membrane structural changes on methane removal efficiency

Fig. S 8. Dissolved methane removal efficiency (RE, %) versus time on stream in degassing tests for PDMS, unaltered PVDF (uPVDF) and altered PVDF (aPVDF) at liquid (Q_L) and sweep gas (Q_{N_2}) flow rates of 3.5 L h^{-1} and 4.0 L h^{-1} , respectively. aPVDF was operated during at least 5 hours at Q_L of 21.0 L h^{-1} before the experiment.

S9. Microscopy analysis on PDMS and PVDF

Morphology of the membrane surface and membrane cross-section were analysed using a Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FESEM) equipped with an Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDX) and applying a voltage of 20 kV (Hitachi S4800, Hitachi Ltd., Japan). For image acquisition, the sample surfaces were coated with a fine layer of Au/Pd by sputtering for 1 minute.

FESEM-EDX analysis was carried out on pristine PDMS and on altered PDMS after 95 hours of time of use with a liquid flow rate (Q_L) of 21.0 L h^{-1} (Fig. S and Fig. S). Cleavages and delamination were observed on the altered PDMS.

Also, FESEM-EDX analysis was carried out on pristine PVDF and on altered PVDF (aPVDF) after 150 hours of time of use with a liquid flow rate (Q_L) of 21.0 L h^{-1} (Fig. S and Fig. S). A less porous surface was observed on the aPVDF attributed to a permanent deformation. Changes inside the membrane can be also observed.

Fig. S 9. Superficial FESEM images of the a) pristine-unaltered and b) altered PDMS membrane. Altered PDMS was operated 95 hours at a liquid flow rate (Q_L) of 21.0 L h^{-1} before the image acquisition.

Fig. S 10. Cross section FESEM images and EDX analysis of the pristine-unaltered PDMS, a1) and a2), and altered PDMS, b1) and b2). Altered PDMS was operated 95 hours at a liquid flow rate (Q_L) of 21.0 L h^{-1} before the image acquisition.

Fig. S 11. Superficial FESEM images of the a) pristine-unaltered and b) altered PVDF. Altered PVDF was operated 150 hours at a liquid flow rate (Q_L) of 21.0 L h^{-1} before the image acquisition.

Fig. S 12. Cross section FESEM images and EDX analysis of the pristine-unaltered PVDF, a1) and a2), and altered PVDF, b1) and b2). Altered PVDF was operated 150 hours at a liquid flow rate (Q_L) of 21.0 L h^{-1} before the image acquisition.

S10. Mass transfer coefficients

Table S1. Mass transfer coefficients at different liquid (Q_L) and sweep gas flow rates (Q_{N_2}) for dense PDMS and microporous PP-1E, PP-2EHF and unaltered PVDF (uPVDF) and altered PVDF (aPVDF). Estimated ($K_{L,est}$) and experimental ($K_{L,exp}$) overall mass transfer coefficients and estimated individual mass transfer coefficients of liquid, membrane and gas phase (k_L , k_m and k_G , respectively) are presented. aPVDF was operated during at least 5 hours at Q_L of 21.0 $L h^{-1}$ before the experiment.

Membrane	Q_L , $L h^{-1}$	Q_{N_2} , $L h^{-1}$	$k_{G,est} \cdot 10^5$ $m s^{-1}$	$k_{m,est} \cdot 10^5$ $m s^{-1}$	$k_{L,est} \cdot 10^5$ $m s^{-1}$	$K_{L,est} \cdot 10^5$ $m s^{-1}$	$K_{L,exp} \cdot 10^5$ $m s^{-1}$
PDMS	27.0	0.05	369.29	29.85	5.03	5.00	4.97 ± 0.18
	3.5	0.50	371.89	29.85	2.25	2.24	2.12 ± 0.18
	21.0	0.50	371.89	29.85	4.54	4.53	4.43 ± 0.24
	27.0	0.50	371.89	29.85	5.03	5.00	4.65 ± 0.20
	40.5	0.50	371.89	29.85	5.87	5.82	6.28 ± 0.18
	27.0	1.50	373.52	29.85	5.03	5.00	5.42 ± 0.12
	27.0	4.00	376.50	29.85	5.03	5.00	4.80 ± 0.18
	27.0	15.00	402.78	29.85	5.03	5.00	4.63 ± 0.18
	3.5	4.00	376.50	29.85	2.25	2.24	2.53 ± 0.14
	21.0	4.00	376.50	29.85	4.54	4.53	4.36 ± 0.24
PP-2EHF	21.0	0.50	371.89	911.45	4.54	4.53	4.59 ± 0.18
PP-1E	21.0	0.50	371.89	1549.46	4.54	4.53	4.05 ± 0.18
	21.0	1.50	373.52	1549.46	4.54	4.53	4.19 ± 0.18
uPVDF	3.5	4.00	376.50	4247.33	2.25	2.24	1.66 ± 0.14
	10.0	4.00	376.50	4247.33	3.41	3.41	3.02 ± 0.18
	21.0	4.00	376.50	4247.33	4.54	4.53	3.70 ± 0.18
aPVDF	3.5	4.00	376.50	4247.33	2.25	2.24	2.18 ± 0.10
	21.0	4.00	376.50	4247.33	4.54	4.53	4.97 ± 0.18

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